

Emotion Recognition: most recent works through EEG signal investigation

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Abstract—The aim of this study is to select some relevant studies that present human emotion recognition investigation through EEG signals by means of novel approaches. Four studies are highlighted, they were selected by means of most citations and recognized journals. With accurate and objective emotion analysis results from electroencephalogram (EEG) data processing approaches, we can chose better methods to work with. Hence, this paper summarizes the most recent works that have converged and diverged in the methods in EEG signal analysis for emotion recognition.

Keywords—*affective brain-computer interface, signal processing, power spectrum, feature extraction.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotion is a psycho-physiological process, which describes momentary aspects of our daily life. Conscious and unconscious triggers activate personality traits, which can be modeled by means of computing approaches. Affective brain-computer interface rises from the intention to make machines interact with our emotion states.

Other types of investigation do not use brain signals to understand emotion recognition (ER), and one type is called “non-physiological clue” [1], e.g., facial expression and gesture, fused expression, speech, and different body aspects together to translate emotion states. Using electroencephalogram (EEG) signals to recognize emotion aspects, immediate responses to emotional stimuli with an excellent temporal resolution can be obtained using direct and comprehensive methods [2].

Emotion recognition can be applied in many fields, such as mental health care, entertainment, society safety purposes, but also in healthcare applications, improving quality of life for many users (e.g., elderly people, chronically ill people and people with severe motor disabilities) and improving quality of experience when applied in research approaches, inside serious games, for example.

Attentional engagement is modulated by emotion states, it can be observed by detecting emotion changes of a subject in an experiment, for example, that requires different levels of engagement. In this sense, attentional engagement relates to how effectively we gather information from a brain-computer interface (BCI) application, for example, also it denotes dominance. Even in situations where there is an absence of competing stimuli, a consistent attentional engagement is a challenge. Therefore, the modulation of neural responses by attentional state has been widely explored, and this aspect is important to relate to ER.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Models and means of working with ER

Stimulus-evoked responses are investigated by several approaches in neuroscience. Naturalistic stimuli studies how the brain processes narratives and how it, conversely, affect mental state [3]. It shows that films actually mimic the real-world environment, changing the perspective of conventional laboratory stimuli.

Many multimodal approaches for ER are available in neuroscience. Most commonly they use audio, visual and audio-visual stimuli. Table 1 shows the most discussed actual affective databases, modified from [4].

TABLE I. USER-CENTERED AFFECTIVE DATABASES [4]

Name	User-Centered Affective Databases		
	Recorded signals	No. subjects	No. stimuli
HUMAINE	audio, visual, physiological	var ^a	var ^a
DEAP [5]	physiological	32	40
DECAF	face, physiological	30	76
MAHNOB-HCI	face, audio, eye gaze, physiological	27	20
ASCERTAIN	face, physiological	58	36

^a. var denotes variable

Despite the fact that film-clips are used to mimic realistic situations, they are intended to evoke target-specific emotion, differing from the naturalistic stimuli approach, requiring user *free-viewing*. Free-viewing definition is attributed to the conditions under which eye movement behavior was not influenced or restricted by the experimenter in some way other than telling participants to perform a task.

Under the current definition, free-viewing could therefore occur in different research interests, from reading to visual search and scene perception [6]. A strategy proposed to work with free-viewing and its extracted Event Related Potentials (ERPs) - averaging EEG measurements - is to combine eye-tracking (ET) signals.

Generally, two existing models of emotion guide researchers to understand and construct an emotional space: the discrete model and the dimension model. The discrete model considers that the emotional space consists of a limited number of basic discrete emotions [2].

Although some viewpoints are not consistent, most studies tend to agree with at least six basic emotions: joy, sadness, surprise, fear, anger, and disgust [7]. On the other hand, the dimensional model divides the emotional space into two (i.e.,

valence-arousal, VA), with standardized types and quantity of stimuli, such as shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Valence reflects the positive and negative characteristics. Arousal reflects the mental vigilance level of emotion and the intensity of physiological activation that an individual feels. Dominance refers to an individual's status: in control or being controlled [2].

B. EEG data processing and toolboxes

Modern, off-the-shelf, wireless, portable and low-cost EEG devices have proposed an increased investigation over BCIs in neural application methods for daily-life requirements and for healthcare applications. For example, an ER EEG-based system can be developed based on process as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. ER EEG-based system modules.

The lower complexity of some off-the-shelf devices often makes it convenient to use and capture EEG, but it can also mean fewer channels and less cortical information recording, reducing data accuracy and system reliability [8].

A few existing studies have implemented real-time EEG-based emotion detection systems (see Table 2), using off-the-shelf devices and standardized emotional stimuli [2].

TABLE II. EXISTING REAL-TIME EEG-BASED EMOTION RECOGNITION SYSTEMS [2]

Reference	All data recorded with EMOTIV® Device		
	Emotion	Stimulus (classes)	Classifier
[9]	audio	2 valence x 3 arousal	SVM ^a
[10]	audio, visual	2 valence	SVM
[11]	visual	2 valence x 2 arousal	SVM
[12]	audio, visual	valence	LDA

^a Support vector machine

Typically, standardized stimuli are selected based on a large sample of participants' subjective feelings and emotional experiences and have been proven to better elicit a single and pure target emotion than those stimuli created relying on a smaller sample size in a single experiment [2].

On the other hand, the majority of research application on EEG-based emotion recognition is using supervised learning algorithms (e.g., SVM, Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest Neighbours) to predict emotional states. Researchers collect a user's self-reported scores on the levels of arousal and valence after presenting emotional stimuli [2]. Then, the user's ratings are separated into two (e.g. low and high) or more classes by selecting the threshold of a 9-point self-assessment rating scale [5]. Therefore, this categorization does not work for real-time recognition of emotion.

For more naturalistic conditions of exploring ER processing, co-registration of other signals, such as eye tracking, provides new paradigms for studying attention, memory encoding, visual search, reading and responses to emotionally charged visual information [13].

In a most recent free-viewing data study [6], the EYE-EEG toolbox was used. Independent Component Analysis (ICA) processing was applied and data imported into MNE-Python toolbox to be processed. A strategy to combine ET-EEG is to read ERP as fixation related potentials (FRPs). It proposes regression analysis to data, but this approach is limited when applied to free-viewing circumstances.

A way of working with combined data is to consider its nonlinearity. GAMM (generalized additive mixed modelling), for example, combines a parametric part with a non-parametric part, which provides nonlinear smoothing functions for modeling. The use of nonlinear regression techniques in modeling ET and ERPs activity is currently in the forefront of co-registration research [13].

Reference [13] highlights Morlet complex wavelets for EEG processing, and evaluates phase-locking of EEG signals to saccade and FRP across EEG epochs. Inter-trial coherence (ITC) phenomena was first proposed by reference [14] and it is given by

$$ITC(f, t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{F_k(f, t)}{|F_k(f, t)|}$$

where n indicates the number of trials, $F_k(f, t)$ is the Fourier component of trial k at frequency f and time t , estimated by Morlet wavelets. ITC values vary between 0 and 1, where 0 indicates no phase-locking and 1 indicates perfect phase-locking.

Summing up, for feature extraction, in previous EEG-ER systems, various features have been used, including common spatial pattern, higher order crossings, time-domain statistical features, EEG spectral power, wavelet entropy, and coherence feature [15]. Among these features, EEG spectral power appears to be the most frequently used feature, however, two limitations should be noted:

- First, with the increases of the number of electrodes and the number of chosen frequency bands, the dimension of the feature vector consisting of the spectral powers from different bands and different electrodes would be very large which increases the computational burden.
- Second, EEG requires high temporal resolution in mapping, so that the EEG spectral power provides a worse representation of the underlying oscillatory brain activity during emotional processing.

Therefore, it is necessary to use a post-processing method to further extract fewer features with higher discriminability from a large number of spectral powers of different bands and electrodes. This can be achieved by using subspace analysis methods, such as principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [15].

III. DISCUSSION

In the end, it should be mentioned that there are several problems concerning the sum up of papers focusing on EEG signals and their applications to ER. As the field is new, standards of analysis and experimentation have not been

established. This makes it difficult to draw clear conclusions when comparing studies that might even be investigating identical conditions.

Furthermore, these mathematically-focused contributions do not always control for physiological variables when obtaining data for classification, and they are often biased. This issue is worsened by the relatively small amount of data that are typically used for these experiments, and a lack of details when reporting on how the data were obtained and its quality.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we highlighted some studies that worked with ER in some types of EEG applications in order to reach a higher accuracy of feature extraction and classification processes.

Some studies issues were mentioned and discussed, as well as the way we put studies information, revealed a lack of standardization when it comes to neuroscience and its application in ER and data processing.

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